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A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE HEART'S EQUATION”

The heart, an unknown variable,
a function that doesn't display truth.
Its range is a living, loving death;
its domain is a brief, tender breath.

A steep, high slope of longing,
meets the flat plane of old passions.
The intersection, one quick kiss,
A remedy for a lifelong happiness.

A parabola of graceful hope,
widens to reveal a soft face.
Its vertex, a quick touch,
A peak with immense significance.

However, observe how a sine wave begins to rise.
pulsing, rhythmic, and time-marking.
With ups and downs of happiness and suffering,
a sun-rain cycle.

The rate of love on a tired face,
the derivative, a fluctuating pace.
From a whispered vow to the arrival of a kingdom,
the integral is the sum total of a life.

Plot your points and draw your line,
a divine truth that is the curve of your heart.
Because the equation of a heart
is contained in this graph of human art.

